

Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets

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Abstract

The volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA) environment has become a part of the norm in modern firms. This study attempts to quantify VUCA in today's market while analysing whether corporate resilience and strategies of modern international firms have changed the historical relationship between volatility and returns. Using daily data from 1995 to 2025 for the S&P 500 covering 80% of the U.S market cap and the STOXX Europe 600 covering 90% of the total market cap in the European continent, the study uses Ordinary Least Squares regression (OLS) to test long-term volatility trends and Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) models to check if the VUCA environment will persist for a long time.

In the past, Volatility was historically inversely related to returns, which is consistent with the low-volatility anomaly. However, through VUCA quantification, the results of this study contribute to existing theories by revealing a significant change: both U.S. and European firms achieved strong positive returns despite elevated volatility. This result is unprecedented in the modern financial system: volatility, even though will remain as an important measure of risk, may no longer capture the capacity of firms to generate high returns in today's modern VUCA world. In other words, since the entire market is VUCA, volatility maybe should no longer be avoided.

1 Introduction

In the past, events that impose a challenge on major companies did occur, every decade or so. Today such events occur monthly, in an environment known by high Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity (VUCA), businesses that survive are considered as successful, while businesses that thrive are considered as a study tool for future generations, to learn how to adapt and compete in the modern competitive global market where tariffs (Contractor, 2025), sanctions (Kaspard et al., 2023) and subsidies (Zhu et al., 2025) are the new norm and market disruptions occur on a more frequent basis.

The main problem is not volatility itself, but the increase in required return due to the increase in risk, which renders the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) of companies higher, this makes companies more susceptible to a weak competitiveness cycle, in which increased cost increases prices, and increased prices reduces quantity sold, and sales reduction increases prices further. These problems are consistent with previous findings in competitive strategy, as rising capital costs results in a reduction of a firm's ability to price competitively which weakens market positioning (Porter, 2008; Brealey, Myers, & Allen, 2020).

Like any other problem, the first step towards a solution is the recognition of a problem, therefore the first purpose of the research is to study market volatility mainly in S&P500 companies to quantify the problem and mathematically calculate VUCA, answering the research question: how high is volatility in the current market environment when compared to previous years?

The second purpose is to monitor the performance of those companies, specifically in recent years when market volatility reached peaks, to examine whether VUCA only amplified risk or also had a significant impact on profitability as well, which allows the study to answer: Are returns significantly affected by this volatility?

The third purpose is to compare European companies with their American counterparts, to answer the question: Is VUCA risk global or specific per continent?

Table 1: Research Questions

	Research Question	Type
1	How high is VUCA Risk when compared to previous years?	Quantitative
2	Are returns significantly affected by Volatility?	Quantitative
3	Is VUCA risk global or specific to continents?	Quantitative

Source: Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets

Answering these research questions, will allow investors to numerically understand the current VUCA environment and the impact of this environment on returns. Specifically, the study will show if risk is amplified in either Europe or the United States to make more informed decisions through better planning (Subrahmanyam, Azoury, & Sarkis, 2024)

.Which would not only help investors but other stakeholders in the companies such as managers and decision makers, enabling them to form better strategies(Bennett & Lemoine, 2014; Damodaran, 2012).

In addition to assisting managers and investors, cheaper access to capital rendering prices lower would positively impact consumers through lower prices, assisting Central banks throughout the world in achieving inflation control objectives.

In addition to the above practical contributions, theoretically the study challenges the traditional current volatility-return relationship agreed upon, according to which, unlike high return, high volatility should be avoided, well as the study will discuss this may not be the case in modern markets.

The structure of the study includes examining literature related to traditional theories from the 1970's and modern theories in from 2025, as well as discussing the interconnection and technological advancements in the modern world, which has attributed to an increase in risk as well as return. This literature is followed by a research methodology that analyse the daily return for 30 years (1995 until 2025), with data focusing on S&P 500 in the United States and comparing it to STOXX 600 in Europe, the results section comparing the 2 indexes is both discussed thoroughly and visualized extensively, followed by both practical recommendations for investors in the conclusion as well as theoretical contributions for scholars.

Last but not least, this study positions volatility not merely as a threat to be mitigated or a danger to be avoided, but as a defining structural feature of contemporary markets that demands renewed analytical frameworks and strategic thinking. By quantifying VUCA risk, examining its implications for returns, and comparing its transmission across the United States and Europe, the research seeks to move beyond subjective discussions toward measurable, decision-relevant insights. In doing so, it invites investors, managers, and policymakers to reconsider long-held assumptions about risk (Beainy et al., 2023), competitiveness, and value creation in an era where instability is no longer episodic but persistent. The findings aim to demonstrate that understanding volatility rather than simply avoiding it, may be the key to sustaining competitiveness, enhancing resilience, and transforming uncertainty into a strategic advantage in the modern global financial landscape.

2 Literature Review

2.1 VUCA and Volatility-Return Relationship

The importance of volatility as a measure of risk is not new, yet the concept of VUCA which combines in addition to Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity is a more recent term. Previously traditional models such as ARCH and GARCH (Engle, 1982; Bollerslev, 1986), could entirely capture the clustering and persistence of volatility, however today VUCA highlights today's speed and the frequency of extreme events also known as tail risks.

From a historical perspective, traditional theories in the far past suggested that investors require a higher return on investment once the volatility or risk is higher (Sharpe, 1964; Lintner, 1965). But more recent studies were able through empirical studies and statistics refute this claim (Haugen & Heins, 1975; Ang et al., 2006), and thus the current low volatility theory was created, according to which in periods of high volatility stocks do not perform well, especially relative to the level of risk. In fact, recent data in the 21st century do support the current theory. New studies (Blitz & van Vliet, 2007; Baker et al., 2011) further reinforce these claims and justify them with leverage limits (Frazzini & Pedersen, 2014), especially since investor sentiments heavily impact prices, particularly in the U.S Market (Khalife et al., 2025).

As apparent, studying the volatility-return relationship has been a top priority, both theoretically for scholars and practically for investors since the US based financial system (Kamel, Beainy, & Bteish, 2025) was created after the second world war, however methods have evolved from purely theoretical and manual to almost fully automated through technology and machine learning, and in a world today where machines learn (Ananthaswamy, 2025), the relationship between volatility and return not only became easier to examine and faster to generate, but also more in-depth and with results more accurate than ever before.

2.2 A world increasingly connected

Globalization obviously has caused volatility to spread easier across different continents, previous literature supported such claims especially in times of crisis (King & Wadhwani, 1990; Bekaert & Harvey, 1997). Forbes and Rigobon (2002) further reinforced those studies through contagion, excess correlation and interdependence, while work by scholars Diebold and Yilmaz (2009, 2014) aimed to provide quantitative evidence of those theories. Fast forward, Wang et al. (2021) reanalyzed the argument using data from the COVID-19 era and reached the same results regarding increased connectedness of volatility around a world where technology is evolving exponentially (Beainy & Kamel, 2023). In fact, Chen and Wang (2023) argue that it is the global variables that explain the majority of the local volatility persistence.

The last two decades provided more than enough data to be able to study volatility worldwide on a new higher level, starting from the dot-com bubble (2000-2002) which was caused by excessive risk taking and over confidence in technological stocks (Schiller, 2005), to the 2008 financial crisis which began small, with mortgage defaults inside the U.S and quickly expanded to cause worldwide bank failures (Reinhart & Rogoff, 2009), to the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic that literally tore apart supply chains and halted labor force in the labor market (IMF, 2020; Baker et al., 2020) to the extent that scholars argue that volatility spillover reached new peaks during COVID-19 (Zhang et al., 2020; Yarovaya et al., 2021). Maybe that is the reason why scholars such as Bennett and Lemoine (2014) argue that organizations must quickly adapt to succeed in highly volatile environments as the failure of one can cause the failure of others, similar to what happened to the silver gate and silicon valley banks (Beainy & Kaspard, 2023). Further discussing connectedness, Xu et al. (2025) analyze dynamic spillovers between volatility indexes across markets, their results show that in 2024 the transmission of shocks accelerated at an alarming pace, which indicates that the traditional

view of volatility, as an idiosyncratic process no longer holds, in fact, in an increasingly connected world, volatility should be viewed and treated as a systemic process, which further highlights the importance and urgency of rethinking the traditional old risk return relationship in a modern world (Beainy, 2023) that is defined by technological advancements, algorithmic complexity, tariffs and immense structural connectivity.

2.3 Better technology but more gaps in the literature

Innovation and technology allowed the creation of new methods to analyze volatility, from the old Markov-switching models (Hamilton, 1989) and stochastic volatility model (Taylor, 1994), to high-frequency data model (Andersen et al., 2003), to the connectedness index which remains widely used till today (Diebold and Yilmaz's 2009, 2014), finally machine learning techniques (Guo et al., 2021) and deep learning models (Han et al., 2022).

This literature trip from past to present only reflect the growing importance of volatility study especially because of the increase in number of investors and the ever increasing market cap, especially in the United States and Europe. However, what is unexpected is that important gaps are in the literature today, because most volatility-return studies end before 2022, because studies after the first two years, studies related to the pandemic had little to no audience as literature was already saturated, leaving few to none studies to discuss whether this resilience that appeared during COVID-19 remained, or even increased in the 2023–2025 VUCA environment. On the other hand, lately empirical advances began to challenge the previously accepted view of stable negative volatility-return relationship, scholars such as Chun, Cho & Ryu (2025) employ machine learning–based volatility forecasting to construct volatility-timing portfolios, finding that such adaptive strategies that actually consist of investing in volatile times, do outperform static benchmarks, especially in high-volatility regimes. These results suggest that volatility, unexpectedly, may serve as a signal for trading rather than a penalty, also through the use of modern technology and Machine learning ML models, Kumar et al. (2025) proposes that volatility, when quantified properly, is becoming increasingly a trading signal not just a risk to avoid.

Studies about volatility are becoming increasingly important, as Artificial intelligence AI and machine learning allowed investors to further try to benefit from price swings, which additionally increase volatility to significantly higher levels, Abbas et al. (2024/2025) states that is due to the widespread adoption of AI-driven trading among investors. The results of this increased used of AI is not only impacting volatility but changing financial fundamentals, as Xing et al. (2025) examine how AI and modern factor models can change the existing the link between volatility risk and expected returns, to the extent that “high beta” stocks would not consistently earn greater returns once machine models are fully integrated in the investment process.

In summary, the literature reveals that even though volatility has always been a significant concept in finance, yet its impact and strength have evolved drastically in the modern VUCA era. Both globalization and technology have transformed volatility from an isolated specific market risk into a systemic global risk that surpasses nations. Technology allowed a greater precision in the measurement of volatility and return, however it did not only serve as an observer to better monitor markets and analyze them, but also as an amplifier that may or may not increase return, but has surely, as backed by empirical evidence, increased volatility.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Data Collection and Methodology

The collected data used in the study were retrieved from NASDAQ (National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations) and Yahoo Finance, using data from 1995 till 2025.

Data were verified using SPDR S&P 500 ETF Trust (SPY) which is the largest ETF in the world tracking the S&P Index.

The reason of the double validation is that S&P 500 is not an exchange traded security but an entire market index of the largest 500 companies in the United States.

Similarly for Europe, the STOXX Europe 600 index was used, to track both the volatility and the performance of the largest companies trading in European continental markets.

Through S&P 500 and STOXX Europe 600, the study will cover over 80% of the entire US market capitalization and over 90% of the European market capitalization (including countries in the European continent but not part of the European Union).

Data analysis was done through Python, Pandas and Numpy with daily return calculated using closing prices and the formula: $R_t = \frac{P_t - P_{t-1}}{P_{t-1}}$. Similarly, volatility was calculated using the sigma (Standard deviation) of the daily returns and then annualized by multiplying the results with the square root of the numbers of working days (in stock markets) per year, using the following formula: $\sigma_{Annual} = \sigma_{Daily} \times \sqrt{252}$. In addition to capture both the short and long time horizons rolling windows volatility were computed over both 30- and 252-days period.

To make sure the results are as accurate as possible, two analyses were conducted on the returns, one related to price only and the second related to total return which includes in addition to changes in prices, dividends.

Furthermore, two statistical methods were used to confirm or reject a current VUCA environment Hypothesis, the first being the ordinary least squares regression (OLS) and the second being a generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity test (GARCH Analysis).

Table 2: Study Data Coverage

Index	Number of Companies	Geographic Coverage	Cover in %
S&P 500	500	United States	Covers over 80% of U.S. market capitalization
STOXX Europe 600	600	17 European countries (Including the United Kingdom and Switzerland)	Covers over 90% of European market capitalization

Source: S&P Dow Jones Indices (2025) STOXX Ltd. (2025).

4 Results and Discussion

In this section, we examine together volatility, return, GARCH and Ordinary least square (OLS) of S&P 500, in which over 80% of the entire U.S market capitalization is included, and in STOXX 600 which is designed to cover approximately 90% of the market capitalization in the European equity market, conclusions are then drawn from the results that are compared to previous findings and theories regarding volatility and return.

4.1 VUCA IN USA

Figure 1: S&P 500 Volatility Annualized

Source: Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets

Figure 2: S&P 500 30 Days Rolling

Source: Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets

As shown in the above figures, three previous periods witnessed higher volatility, the first being the 2002 dot com bubble, a market turmoil that was driven by over speculative investing in internet companies, this caused the NASDAQ stock market index to fall nearly 80% of its 2000 peak (Shiller, 2005). The second being the 2008 financial crisis which, even though was first initiated by the real estate sector, quickly spread and became global and caused international bank failure and recession throughout the world (Reinhart & Rogoff, 2009). And the third being the Covid-19 recession, with trading halted after extreme declines in the Black Monday and the black Thursday (IMF, 2020). Today once again, VUCA knocks, yet not due to a natural disaster nor because of failures in the financial system, in fact the huge volatility nowadays is the results of a combination of policies, tariffs, sanctions and protectionism, even in some cases influencers ((Mawad & Freiha, 2024) (Sarkis, Maalouf & Lakiss, 2024) which may or may be not positive on the long run, but on the short run, seems like a self-inflicted VUCA pandemic.

Table 3: Ordinary least square analysis

US Volatility Trend Regression (Vol ~ Year):						
OLS Regression Results						
Dep. Variable:	vol		R-squared:	0.000		
Model:	OLS		Adj. R-squared:	-0.034		
Method:	Least Squares		F-statistic:	0.0008363		
Date:	Sun, 21 Sep 2025		Prob (F-statistic):	0.977		
Time:	01:21:49		Log-Likelihood :	36.359		
No. Observations:	31		AIC:	-68.72		
Df Residuals:	29		BIC:	-65.85		
Df Model:	1		Covariance Type:	Nonrobust		
	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
const	0.2642	3.125	0.085	0.933	-6.127	6.656
year	-4.496e-05	0.002	-0.029	0.977	-0.003	0.003
Omnibus:	12.102		Durbin-Watson:	1.571		
Prob(Omnibus):	0.002		Jarque-Bera (JB):	11.395		
Skew:	1.255		Prob(JB):	0.00335		
Kurtosis:	4.589		Cond. No.:	4.52e+05		

Source: *Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets*

The OLS of U.S. annualized volatility on year from 1995 to 2025 provided an insignificant slope $\beta = -0.0043$, with power value $p = 0.637$, and $R^2 = 0.008$. These findings are consistent with crisis-driven VUCA dynamics such as Covid-19 earlier and current tariffs and sanctions.

Figure 3: S&P 500 Return (Share Price Only)

Source: Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets

Figure 4: S&P 500 Return (Price + Dividends)

Source: Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets

Figure 5: S&P 500 Rolling Return

Source: Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets

Unlike the previous high volatility periods of 2002, 2008 and 2020, S&P 500 returns during this VUCA Period remained positive, which shows that American companies acquired greater resilience to financial challenges. In fact, even in 2023 and 2024, Price return remained above 20%, with 24.23 and 23.31% consecutively, and total return above 25% with 26.29 and 25.02% respectively.

In fact, when compared to previous period, earlier studies labelled this increase in returns after 2021 as “jumps” in S&P 500 performance, Khashanah, Chen, Buckle, and Hawkes (2025) argue that this increase is caused by the individual performance of specific companies within the S&P 500 index, such as the magnificent seven, such as Apple, Microsoft, Alphabet, Amazon, Nvidia, Meta and Tesla.

Table 4: GARCH Analysis

US GARCH(1,1) summary:					
Zero Mean - GARCH Model Results					
Dep. Variable:	Return		R-squared:	0.000	
Mean Model:	Zero Mean		Adj. R-squared:	0.000	
Vol Model:	GARCH		Log-Likelihood:	-10461.8	
Distribution:	Normal		AIC:	20929.6	
Method:	Maximum Likelihood		BIC:	20950.4	
Date:	Sun, Sep 21 2025		No. Observations:	7547	
Time:	01:21:55		Df Residuals:	7547	
			Df Model:	0	
Volatility Model	coef	std err	t	P> t	95.0% Conf. Int.
omega	0.0225	4.370e-07	5.159	2.485e-07	[1.398e-02, 3.111e-02]
alpha[1]	0.1135	1.098e-02	10.339	4.696e-25	[9.200e-02, 0.135]
beta[1]	0.8705	1.146e-02	75.962	0.000	[0.848, 0.893]

Source: *Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets*

The GARCH(model for U.S. returns provided significant results for the ARCH term alpha and the GARCH term Beta. Because their value is almost one (0.984) this reinforce the thesis that we are in a VUCA time and the result is statistically significant at the 95% level.

Table 5: Price and Annual Return

Year	Price Annual Return	Total Annual Return	Note
1995	34.16	37.62	
1996	20.26	22.96	
1997	31.01	33.36	
1998	26.67	28.58	

1999	19.53	21.04	
2000	-10.14	-9.1	High Volatility Period
2001	-13.04	-11.89	
2002	-23.37	-22.1	
2003	26.38	28.68	
2004	8.99	10.88	
2005	3	4.91	
2006	13.62	15.79	
2007	3.53	5.49	
2008	-38.49	-37	High Volatility Period
2009	23.45	26.46	
2010	12.78	15.06	
2011	0	2.11	
2012	13.41	16	
2013	29.6	32.39	
2014	11.39	13.69	
2015	-0.73	1.38	
2016	9.54	11.96	
2017	19.42	21.83	
2018	-6.24	-4.38	
2019	28.88	31.49	
2020	16.26	18.4	
2021	26.89	28.71	
2022	-19.44	-18.11	High Volatility Period
2023	24.23	26.29	
2024	23.31	25.02	
2025	13.31	14.39	High Volatility Period

Source: *The Impact of VUCA on Return*

To answer the second research question, yes, historically returns have historically been inversely proportional to volatility based on the low-volatility anomaly (Haugen & Heins, 1975; Ang et al., 2006) except in the 2025 VUCA Period where companies succeeded despite the high volatility, which is significant and happened for the first time in our modern financial system. When compared to earlier results, the study does not presume that previous literature and assumptions are no longer valid, for until the high return – high volatility scenario in 2025 is repeated, these new findings are an exception not a norm, however it is worth noting that the current equity market situation, supported by the Artificial Intelligence (AI) technological breakthrough, exhibit risk return characteristics that are relatively new, and this is not only impacting firms directly related to the technological sectors, but has also positive externalities on non-technological firms as well (Kamel, Kaspard & Khalil, 2023).

4.2 VUCA in Europe

Figure 6: Volatility of STOXX Europe (20 Years)

Source: *Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets*

Figure 7: Index Price Level of STOXX Europe (30 Years)

Source: *Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets*

Figure 8: S&P (USA) and Stoxx (Europe) Volatility

Source: Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets

In terms of Volatility, the above figures show that any volatility is cross continental, any increase in volatility in the American market is directly reflected in the European market and vice versa. Volatility risk in S&P 500 is directly proportional to that of Stoxx 600, which may be a cause of the increased globalization. This answers the research question three “Is VUCA risk global or specific to continents?” VUCA risk is global, and investors cannot avoid volatility by simply shifting the geographical location of their investments between continents.

This study does highlight an increase in volatility after the 2008 crisis, especially in the United States which has a significant impact on the entire financial system (Beainy et Al., 2025), yet according to other research articles and results VUCA’s impact is not always negative, in fact Athari et. Al. 2023 argue that volatility and vulnerability can be drivers to innovation and corporate resilience, because companies must adapt to these changing environments both to survive and to succeed, additionally, mathematical results in the figures above do support these theories, as we notice an increase in return especially in the previous two decades.

Finally, earlier studies (Georges, 2014) do report this correlation between US and European markets, even though according though when comparing results, this correlation is lower between the American and the Asian market, more particularly with the Chinese equity market.

Beyond these direct transmission mechanisms, the persistence of the volatility which can be described as synchronized, suggest the presence of new, deep structural linkages in between the transatlantic markets, the result is simple, VUCA is now global, but the reasons are far more complex, those reasons can include but are not limited to financial integration, cross-listing practices, immense multinational corporate exposures and last but not least, the dominance of US-European institutional investors (Such as Blackrock and Vanguard), together, all these reasons contribute to a unified shock-propagation architecture which does not only spread volatility, but also amplifies it.

4.3 Cross-Market Correlation Analysis

The following analysis examines the relationship between major global equity indices, the S&P 500 (US), the EURO STOXX 50 (Europe), and the Shanghai Composite (China), correlation is analysed across two separate dimensions: daily returns and rolling 30-day volatility, later in this section, the two dimensions are merged.

Figure 9: Correlation of Return (10 years)

USA (S&P 500)	1	0.57	0.17
Europe (EU Stoxx 50)	0.57	1	0.23
China (Shanghai composite)	0.17	0.23	1
	USA (S&P 500)	Europe (EU Stoxx 50)	China (Shanghai composite)

Source: *Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets*

Correlation of Daily Returns

The first heatmap above illustrates the Pearson correlation coefficients for daily returns over a 10-year period. This metric reflects how closely the prices of these markets move together on a day-to-day basis. US and Europe: Show a moderate-to-strong positive correlation (0.57). This suggests that while these markets are distinct, they are frequently influenced by similar global macroeconomic trends and investor sentiment, and further enhances the study's findings. While the Shanghai Composite displays a weak correlation with both the US (0.17) and Europe (0.23). This indicates that the Chinese market operates with a high degree of independence, likely driven by localized regulatory environments and domestic economic policies rather than global market shifts.

Figure 10: Correlation of Volatility (10 years)

USA (S&P 500)	1	0.86	0.34
Europe (EU Stoxx 50)	0.86	1	0.35
China (Shanghai composite)	0.34	0.35	1
	USA (S&P 500)	Europe (EU Stoxx 50)	China (Shanghai composite)

Source: *Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets*

The second heatmap in the figure above shifts the focus from price direction to market risk, measured in this study as volatility. This measures whether periods of high fear or instability in one market coincide with similar periods in another. There is a very high correlation (0.86) in rolling volatility between the US and Europe. While their daily returns move together only moderately, their fear cycles are almost identical. When one market becomes volatile, the other almost invariably follows suit quickly, further supporting the previous results. China remains an outlier even in terms of volatility. Its volatility correlation with the US (0.34) and Europe (0.35) is significantly lower than the Western pair. This suggests that shocks to the Chinese financial system do not necessarily transmit to Western markets, and vice versa.

Table 6: Comparative Correlation (10 years)

Market Pair	Daily Returns Correlation	Rolling Volatility Correlation	Difference
US / Europe	0.57	0.86	+0.29
US / China	0.17	0.34	+0.17
Europe / China	0.23	0.35	+0.12

Source: *Volatility and Returns in VUCA Transatlantic Markets*

Key findings highlight the Volatility Contagion Effect: In all cases, the correlation of volatility is higher than the correlation of returns. This supports the financial theory that

while markets may not always go up together, they frequently panic together. Since this study focuses on Transatlantic markets, it is worth mentioning that specifically the US and European markets are deeply integrated, particularly regarding risk profiles. Investors should be aware that holding both does not significantly diversify tail risk or volatility exposure.

5 Conclusion

While aiming to analyse the existence of a current VUCA environment in the market, this study confirmed that this volatility and uncertainty is global. For a Period of 30 years, both volatility and return moved proportionally in the U.S and European markets.

Even though previous increase in volatility occurred during the dot-com bubble (2002), the global financial crisis (2008), and the COVID-19 recession (2020), the current VUCA risk is driven by crisis and is not a periodically repeatable situation. However, the current VUCA environment might persist longer than an expected, according to the alpha and beta results of the GARCH model provided.

In the past, the inversely proportional relationship between volatility and returns was the norm according to the “low-volatility anomaly” theory. However, the results for the 2025 VUCA period signs a significant change in the existing theory. Even with the high levels of volatility, both U.S. firms (measured through S&P 500) and European firms (measured through STOXX Europe 600) achieved significant positive returns.

For investors, since return remained high (both in terms of share price and dividends), traditional risk metrics may no longer be accurate or may to say the least underestimate the strength and resilience of modern companies especially versus systematic risk.

For managers, the results of the study show that to be competitive, companies should not only survive hard situations but even achieve results through strategically using opportunities when the market is highly volatile.

This research covered over 80% of the U.S market capitalization and 90% of that of Europe, future research can extend this analysis by studying as well African, Australian and Asian markets. In addition, the historical resilience achieved by American and European companies can be further explored and developed to further assist companies including small and medium sized enterprises (Khalife, Subrahmanyam, & Farah, 2024), not only to survive, but to excel and thrive, in a new VUCA environment.

Finally, a limitation of this study that can be enhanced in future literature, is the specific impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on volatility and return, as the revolution in artificial intelligence may be the new cause of this significant increase (Chaanine et al., 2023), in both volatility and return.

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